

Potentiometric Study of the Schiff Base Complexes of Copper, Zinc and Mercury

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The study of the complexation reaction of the metals, viz., Copper, Zinc, Mercury with a Schiff base, derived from salicylaldehyde and tris buffer has been carried out. The values of the logarithm of stability constants of complexes and thermodynamic functions are varying in the studied temperature range are as :

For Cu^{2+} $\log \beta$: 5.3 to 4.8; ΔG : -7.45 to -7.1 K.Cal;

ΔH : -13.90 K.cal; ΔS = -21.0 e.u.
(Temp. 34°C to 50°C)

Zn^{2+} $\log \beta$: 5.0 to 4.7; ΔG : -7.02 to -6.78 K. cal.;

ΔH : -16.6 K.cal; ΔS : -31.2 e.u.
(Temp. 34°C to 42°C)

Hg^{2+} $\log \beta$: 4.85 to 4.75; ΔG : -6.81 to -6.85 K.cal;

ΔH : -5.53 K.cal; ΔS = 4.18 e.u.
(Temp. 34°C to 42°C).

SEVERAL workers have reported the use of trisbuffer as a complexing agent^{1,2}. In the present work, a Schiff base has been prepared from salicylaldehyde and tris buffer i.e., tris (hydroxy methyl) amino methane according to the method reported³. Complexation of this pentadentate Schiff base with copper, zinc and mercury has been studied potentiometrically. Stability constants and the thermodynamic parameters have been calculated.

Experimental

'AR' grade chemicals were used. All the solutions were freshly prepared in conductivity water and deaerated with purified nitrogen. The prepared ligand was purified and recrystallized from methanol. Observed m.p. $134 \pm 1^\circ$. Systronics expanded scale pH meter type 331 with Beckman glass and saturated calomel electrodes were used for pH measurements. The specified temperature was attained within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ with Toshniwal constant temperature bath type GL 15.

Three different sets, viz., (1) 0.01M HNO_3 , (2) 0.01M HNO_3 + 0.002M ligand and (3) 0.01M HNO_3 + 0.002M ligand + 0.00067M metal (except Zn, where the metal concentration was 0.002M), were titrated vs carbon dioxide free 1.0M NaOH. The final volume was adjusted to 75.0 ml and the ionic strength $\mu = 0.1 \text{ KNO}_3$ in each set.

Results and Discussion

To calculate the ligand-proton stability constants and metal-ligand stability constants the equations given by Irving and Rosotti^{4,5} were applied. With the present ligand, the number of displaceable protons is equal to 2, because here, besides the phenolic --OH group, the alcoholic --OH group in the amine also dissociates to give up the proton, as investigated by Rustagi, *et al.*³

The formation curves at different temperatures, for the metal complexes were drawn and the nature of the same at 34° is shown in Fig. 1. The curves extend upto 1 in each case, which clearly indicate the formation of 1 : 1 complex. Stability constants were obtained at $\bar{n} = 0.5$.

The experimental results are tabulated as below :

TABLE 1—PROTON LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

Temp.	Log β_1	Log β_2
34°C	9.8	8.0
42°C	9.3	7.5
50°C	9.0	7.6

TABLE 2—LOG OF STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES

Temp.	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Hg^{2+}
34°C	5.3	5.0	4.85
42°C	5.1	4.7	4.75
50°C	4.8	—	—

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Fig. 1

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

	ΔF K.Cal.	ΔH K.Cal.	ΔS Cal.
Cu ²⁺	34°C	-7.45	-21.0
	42°C	-7.35	-13.90
	50°C	-7.1	-21.0
Zn ²⁺	34°C	-7.02	-16.60
	42°C	-6.78	-
Hg ²⁺	34°C	-6.81	+4.18
	42°C	-6.85	+4.18

Several Schiff bases have been prepared from the tris-buffer with different aldehydes and further investigation is in progress.

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